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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Transnational Access to plasma beam testing facilities

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ABSTRACT

This report summarizes the activity of WP13, which objectives were to provide Transnational Access to the plasma beam testing facilities: APOLLON, LPA-UHI100 and LULAL. The WP includes 3 tasks:

- Task 13.1. APOLLON
- Task 13.2. LPA-UHI100
- Task 13.3. LULAL

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Plasma beam testing WP provided access to three different facilities, in France (CEA-LIDYL-UH1100 and CNRS-LULI-APOLLON) and in Sweden (LUND University- LULAL). Electron beams driven by laser wakefields in plasmas with energies ranging from 100MeV to multi-GeV were delivered.

Selected users were funded by the ARIES grant to access the host facility of their choice after their proposal was positively evaluated by the user selection panel.

A total of 7 projects were funded (1146 hours).

Electrons beams from plasmas were used to explore positron generation up to the GeV range, and the generation of efficient betatron X-ray sources. For the first time, a full X-ray tomography was conducted for sprays of realistic automotive fuel injectors at different points in time after start of injection. Testing a plasma accelerator source for EuPRAXIA was investigated to produce high-quality electron beams from a laser plasma wakefield accelerator using a novel plasma source, to characterize the influence of the input laser and plasma beam properties on the generated electron beams, and to explore the influence of laser pulse coupling on the electron injection mechanism.

1. Description of infrastructure

1.1 APOLLON

LULI is the host of APOLLON laser facility. APOLLON is a unique new multi-PW facility, based on a Ti-sapphire laser technology. This facility was opened to ARIES users for testing novel electron acceleration concepts to optimize electron bunch parameters for specific applications, test innovative methods to measure its characteristics or to manipulate it, study electron beam – plasma coupling processes (including synchronization and stability), etc.

During the second period, the commissioning of the APOLLON facility has progressed well on the laser side which delivered to the experimental area a laser beam of peak energy 18J, with a pulse duration of 22fs.

After a long wait for the green light from the French Nuclear Safety Authority for commissioning the electron beam, permission was granted at the beginning of the third period. An electron beamline was implemented and commissioned using the so called F2, PW class beam focused in a gas cell. Using a relatively short 3m focusing length, and 5J of laser energy, electrons beams in the GeV range were achieved.

During the last 12 months a User proposal was selected and a successful experiment performed at the facility using up to 15J of laser energy in a gas cell, and achieving electron beams with maximum energies close to 2 GeV. Using a converter in the path of this beam, positrons in the GeV range were generated and measured. Data analysis is in progress.

1.2 LPA-UH100

LPA-UH100 installation provides ARIES users access to an electron beamline operating around 75 MeV and an experimental area dedicated to laser-driven electron acceleration studies in plasma media. The environment and assistance provided to users was described in the first report.

1.3 LULAL

LULAL (Lund University Laser Acceleration Laboratory) is located at the Lund High Power Laser Facility which is a major infrastructure for research using advanced ultra-short and ultra-intense lasers. It is part of the Lund Laser Centre (LLC), which is the largest unit in the Scandinavian countries in the field of lasers. The research at LLC encompasses a wide range of disciplines ranging from medicine to physics. It also includes laser activities at the 3 GeV synchrotron at the MAX IV Laboratory. The LLC is characterised by its interdisciplinary nature, fostering a strong exchange of ideas, techniques and resources. The laboratory houses one of the most intense ultrafast lasers in Europe. The research at LULAL specialises in laser-driven beams of coherent and incoherent x-rays, fast ions and high-energy electrons. In particular, the facility is instrumental for a strong and very successful research programme on laser-based particle acceleration.

1.4 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE

A User Selection Panel (USP) common to WP13 facilities was constituted. The selection Procedure for the three facilities of this WP followed the steps announced on the ARIES website. **Step1- Informal request:** The User Group Leaders contact the facility coordinator before beginning the formal application process in order to discuss the technical aspects and feasibility of the project and the eligibility of the user group.

Step2-Application form: The User Group Leaders download, fill and submit centrally the application form on the ARIES website. Application forms are directed to the relevant TA WP-coordinator. The user groups interested in beam tests at one of the WP13 TA facilities must request access by submitting (in writing) to the ARIES WP13 User Selection Panel (USP) a description of the work that they wish to carry out for testing of and the names, nationalities and home institutions of the users.

Step3- Selection procedure: After submission, proposals are sent to at least one of the external experts of the USP for reviewing, based on scientific merit, impact, feasibility and ability of the users' team to carry out the proposed work. The User Group Leader is contacted by the ARIES TNA Office regarding the outcome of the selection.

In the case of APOLLON, proposals are also submitted to the facility call for proposals and examined by the scientific programme committee.

The scheduling of experiments is managed locally by each facility.

2. Summary of TA provided

APOLLON	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1- (M1-M18)	0	0	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0	0	0
Period 3 (M37-M60)	1	1	5	30
Total		1	5	30
<i>Foreseen for project (M1-M60)</i>	1		3	0

LPA-UHI100	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1- (M1-M18)	1	1	5	152
Period 2 (M19-M36)	1	1	6	176
Period 3 (M37-M60)	0	0	0	0
Total		2	11	328
<i>Foreseen for project (M1-M60)</i>	3		16	488

LULAL	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1- (M1-M18)	1	1	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2	20	517
Period 3 (M37-M60)	1	1	10	271
Total		4	30	788
<i>Foreseen for project (M1-M60)</i>	5		30	768

3. Highlights of TA results

Plasma beam testing facilities have achieved successful results:

APOLLON has delivered electron beams in P3, soon after commissioning of the facility. High-charge electron beams with maximum energies of the order of the 2 GeV were consistently accelerated in a stable and repeatable manner. These electron beams were then made to interact with high-Z solid targets, producing high-energy positron beams. **The team obtained the highest positron energy ever achieved in a laser-driven configuration, exceeding the GeV.** Moreover, the team was able to comprehensively characterize the spatial and spectral properties of the positron beams. The quantities simultaneously measured were spectrum, charge, and energy dependent source size, divergence, and emittance.

Two projects at LPA UHI100 in P1 and P2 were devoted to the development of positron sources. as A laser-driven source of low-energy positrons would be of interest for high-resolution non-disruptive inspection of materials. This field is of general interest for advanced accelerators development and particularly for the development of dedicated PALS (Positron-Annihilation-Lifetime-Spectroscopy) in modern large-scale plasma-based accelerator projects. **Laser Plasma Accelerated electron beam (up to 200MeV) were used to generate an electron-positron source from quantum cascade in a high Z- converter.** The aim of the experiment was firstly to generate a dense population of ultra-short positrons around MeV energy (from few keV to few MeV). The users, assisted by the local team, have put a lot of effort on the positron source generation and optimisation, from conversion into a Pb target of a stabilised electron beam from laser-plasma acceleration in a gas cell. The secondary electron beam was observed after having optimised the shielding of the diagnostics, which is a key point for this kind of experiment. The positron beam has not been characterised as the particle density was practically under the detection threshold of the diagnostic.

One project at LULAL in P2 was dedicated to **characterize the sprays of realistic automotive fuel injectors at high injection pressure** via X-ray absorption tomography as well as 2-photon LIF (laser-induced fluorescence), Mie-scattering and Shadowgraphy.

For the first time, a full X-ray tomography was conducted for sprays of realistic automotive fuel injectors at different points in time after start of injection. 2D-measurements of the liquid distribution were conducted for the same sprays using 2-photon LIF and Shadowgraphy for comparison. With these measurements, a detailed characterization of the spray structure is possible. The data set provides new insights into the complex spray processes for an improved understanding.

During a second project at LULAL in P2 **Multistage Laser and Beam Driven Plasma accelerator** was studied in order to improve on the efficiency of tabletop X-ray sources of Laser Plasma Wakefield Accelerators (LWFA). The main objectives were to test new, multi-stage, tailored gas targets, optimized for LWFA and plasma X-ray wiggler radiation. Six different geometries of single jets and nozzle arrays were tested. The analysis of experimental data and numerical simulation has shown **increased efficiency of X-ray radiation** due to the formation of a gas density grid created by colliding jets. The collected data will be used for the optimization of micronozzle geometry and radiation efficiency of the tabletop X-ray sources. The laser-assisted fabrication technology of the

micronozzles from single fused silica block ensured high precision, resistance to optical damage, and the formation of tailored plasma profiles with the dimensions of less than 40 μm with nozzle surface roughness $< 1 \mu\text{m}$.

The objectives of **testing plasma accelerator source for EuPRAXia at LULAL in P2** were to produce high-quality electron beams from a laser plasma wakefield accelerator using a novel plasma source, characterize the influence of the input laser and plasma beam properties on the generated electron beams, and explore the influence of laser pulse coupling on the electron injection mechanism. **Low energy spread and low divergence electrons were successfully generated through control of the laser and plasma properties.** A detailed parameter scan was conducted, which can reveal the underlying physical processes and how they influence injection and acceleration in the plasma. Extensive measurement and variation of the input laser pulse properties (energy, spatial phase, spectral phase) allow for the influence of laser evolution in the plasma to be studied, and how this influences the electron beam properties.

In a follow-up campaign in P3 at LULAL, the influence of the entrance, exit density gradients and gas composition (H_2/N_2 mixture) on the laser-plasma accelerated electron beams was studied. It was found that **the optimal combination of these parameters, reproducibly lead to remarkably stable, monoenergetic, high-quality electron beams.** A machine learning algorithm was developed which incorporates detailed control of the laser system, including adaptive optics and an acousto-optic pulse modulator. This was used to optimize the laser-plasma accelerator performance and demonstrating generation of electron beams with tailored qualities (e.g. energy spread and charge).

4. List of TA project

Project acronym	Main objectives	Access units
Emittance characterisation of laser-driven positron beams for injection in conventional accelerators ARIES-CEA-LIDyL-2017-01	Stabilisation and focusing of a laser-driven electron beam Characterisation of an injection-quality positron beam	152
Laser-driven low-energy positrons for high-resolution non-disruptive inspection of materials	Generate a dense population of ultra-short positrons around MeV energy (from few keV to few MeV).	176

ARIES-CEA-LIDyL-2018-01		
MuLaBePA (Multistage Laser and Beam Driven Plasma Accelerator) ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2018-01	Implementation and testing of multistage tailored gas targets for combined electron acceleration in LWFA and Plasma Wakefield Accelerator (PWFA) regime. The project aims at more efficient acceleration of electrons, and the design of betatron sources with increased critical energy.	135
Testing plasma accelerator source for EuPRAXIA ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2018-02	Production of high quality electron beams from a laser plasma wakefield accelerator using a novel plasma source. Characterization of the influence of the input laser and plasma beam properties on the generated electron beams. Exploration of the influence on laser pulse coupling on the electron injection mechanism.	244
Spray imaging with laser driven X-Ray ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2019-01	characterize the sprays of realistic automotive fuel injectors at high injection pressure via X-ray absorption tomography as well as 2-photon LIF (laser-induced fluorescence), Mie-scattering and Shadowgraphy.	138
Testing plasma accelerator source for EuPRAXIA 2 ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2020-01	Examine the electron beam quality and reproducibility from laser-driven plasma wakefield acceleration in a configurable plasma source (a gas cell designed for the EuPRAXIA collaboration fed with a mixture of H ₂ /N ₂).	271
Generation of laser-driven GeV-scale high-quality positron beams ARIES-CNRS-LULI-2021-01	Laser-wakefield acceleration of high-energy (~2GeV) and high-charge (~100s of pC) electron beams; Laser-driven generation and comprehensive characterization of high-quality (sub-micron emittance) GeV-scale positron beams; Laser-driven generation of high-density neutral electron-positron beams	30

5. List of TA publications

TA Project Acronym	Publication Year	Authors	Title	References	Publication type	Peer reviewed	DOI	Open Access
ARIES-CEA-LIDyL-2017-01	2020	A. Alejo, G. Samarin, J. Warwick, C. McCluskey, G. Cantono, T. Ceccotti, S. Dobosz Dufrénoy, P. Monot, G. Sarri	Non-invasive characterisation of a laser-driven positron beam	Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion, 62 055013 (2020)	Journal publication	yes	https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6587/ab7e81	yes
ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2018-01	2020	V. Tomkus, V. Girdauskas, J. Dudutis, P. Gečys, V. Stankevič, G. Račiukaitis, I. Gallardo González, D. Guénot, J. Björklund Svensson, A. Persson, O. Lundh,	“Laser wakefield accelerated electron beams and betatron radiation from multijet gas targets”,	Scientific Reports, 10 , 16807 (2020).	Journal publication	yes	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73805-7	yes
ARIES-ULUND-LULAL-2019-01	2021	H. Ulrich, B. Lehnert, D. Guénot, K. Svendsen, O. Lundh, S. Will, M. Wensing, E. Berrocal, L. Zigan	Analysis of liquid spray structures using two-photon fluorescence laser sheet imaging	ICLASS 2021, Vol. 1 No. 1, Edinburgh, UK, 2021	conference proceeding	Yes	https://doi.org/10.2218/iclass.2021.6139	Yes